
Simplified Learning: ILOK (Instructional Lesson Outline for Kids) Approach for Araling Panlipunan 5

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Summary— The paper, titled "Simplified Learning: ILOK Approach for Araling Panlipunan 5," detailed an educational innovation developed by Rosemarie T. Realino, PhD, at Francisco Bustamante Central Elementary School, implemented in the third quarter of the 2023-2024 school year. The innovation aimed to address challenges in teaching and learning Araling Panlipunan, where students struggled with retaining historical facts and comprehending complex social studies concepts. The ILOK (Instructional Lesson Outline for Kids) approach provided a structured, simplified weekly lesson outline, breaking down complex topics into manageable, easily digestible pieces. This methodology employed thematic and chronological organization, focusing on pivotal events, figures, and concepts to facilitate better understanding and long-term retention. The innovation leveraged visual aids, summaries, and interactive elements to enhance engagement and comprehension. By incorporating both traditional teaching methods and modern educational technologies, ILOK created an interactive and dynamic learning environment. The approach aligned with the Department of Education's vision of fostering inclusive and quality education, promoting critical thinking, and nurturing responsible citizens. The implementation involved several key steps: identifying curriculum objectives, creating lesson outlines, producing and distributing materials, delivering interactive lessons, and conducting assessments and feedback sessions. Teachers played a crucial role in the effective execution of ILOK, managing the resources efficiently and continuously adapting the materials based on student feedback. The project emphasized the importance of strategic planning, collaboration among stakeholders, and iterative refinement to ensure the innovation's success and sustainability. The results indicated improved student engagement, enhanced understanding of Araling Panlipunan concepts, and higher proficiency levels. The innovation demonstrated the potential for broader application in other educational contexts and subjects, contributing significantly to the holistic development of students and the improvement of educational practices.

Keywords— Approach, Educational Innovation, Iterative Refinement, Student Engagement

I. OVERVIEW

In primary education, particularly in Araling Panlipunan 5, educators and learners face multifaceted challenges that hinder effective teaching and learning. Research by Wang, Haertel, and Walberg (1990) highlights that students often struggle with retaining historical facts and comprehending complex social studies concepts, which can lead to disengagement and lower proficiency levels. Furthermore, studies by Darling-Hammond (2000) and Fullan (2001) emphasize that limited access to resources, coupled with traditional pedagogical approaches, exacerbates these challenges by failing to meet the diverse learning needs of students. Additionally, research on student engagement and learning outcomes by Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2004) underscores the importance of interactive and student-centered learning experiences in fostering more profound understanding and reten-

tion of subject matter. These findings collectively underscore the critical need for innovative educational strategies, such as the Instructional Lesson Outline for Kids (ILOK), to address the identified challenges and enhance learning outcomes in Araling Panlipunan.

The Instructional Lesson Outline for Kids (ILOK) emerges as a ground breaking solution designed to address these educational challenges head-on. ILOK leverages simplified lesson outlines and memory-enhancing techniques to make learning more engaging and effective for young learners. By breaking down complex topics into manageable, easily digestible pieces, ILOK facilitates better understanding and long-term retention of facts and concepts. This pedagogical approach provides a structured and simplified weekly lesson outline to make complex subjects more accessible to Grade 5 students. ILOK employs a thematic and chronological organization, breaking topics into pivotal events, figures, and concepts with specific focus areas each week. This method facilitates a systematic and incremental learning process, allowing for better comprehension and memory retention of historical, geographical, and Araling Panlipunan ma-

terials. Through this structured approach, ILOK effectively enhances learners' engagement and understanding, aligning with the educational goals of simplifying learning processes and improving proficiency in Araling Panlipunan.

ILOK's methodology harmoniously aligns with the Department of Education's vision of fostering inclusive and quality education for all. It embodies the mission to nurture critical thinkers and responsible citizens through enhanced comprehension of Araling Panlipunan. Furthermore, ILOK mirrors the core principles and values of the SDO's mantra, promoting a learner-centered, sustainable, and innovative educational environment. By addressing the specific needs of Araling Panlipunan 5 learners, ILOK contributes significantly to uplifting this often-neglected learning area, paving the way for a more educated and empowered youth.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

The ILOK approach is a well-structured educational framework that simplifies complex subjects for Grade 5 students. It involves thematic and chronological teaching strategies focusing on key historical, geographical, and social concepts. This innovative teaching approach incorporates various visual aids, outlines, summaries, and interactive elements to enhance students' understanding and retention of the subject matter.

ILOK simplifies learning by breaking down topics into manageable segments, encouraging a step-by-step exploration of subjects. This method ensures a cohesive and comprehensive learning experience, actively engaging students in the material.

Compared to traditional teaching methods, ILOK provides a more structured and focused approach, which enhances students' comprehension of complex concepts. Its organized format promotes memory retention and encourages active learning, improving learning outcomes.

ILOK combines traditional teaching methods and modern educational technologies to create an interactive and dynamic learning environment. This blend of methodologies enhances the academic experience, making it more engaging and practical for students. By modern educational technologies, we refer to the software and applications used for creating, formatting, and printing educational content. This includes word processing, spreadsheet, and presentation software, which are utilized to design lesson outlines, create engaging content, and organize information in a visually appealing and accessible manner for students. These tools enable the customization of learning materials to cater to different learning styles and needs.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The Simplified Learning: ILOK Approach for Araling Panlipunan 5 aims to enhance students' understanding and retention of historical and social studies concepts while making learning more engaging and accessible. The primary objectives of this innovative approach are to improve proficiency levels in Araling Panlipunan 5 and to address challenges in traditional teaching methods. The ILOK approach provides structured and simplified lesson outlines that cater to diverse learning styles, encouraging active participation and foster-

ing a deeper connection with the material.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The Simplified Learning: ILOK Approach for Araling Panlipunan 5 process flow involved several vital interconnected steps to ensure effective translation of critical elements of the curriculum into accessible content, engaging delivery, and accurate measurement of their impact for iterative refinement.

The first step was identifying critical topics and objectives from the Araling Panlipunan 5 curriculum to cover in the ILOK material through Curriculum Mapping and Content Identification. Once the topics were determined, the next step was to create weekly lesson outlines using simplified language and structured formats, incorporating visual aids, summaries, and critical questions in Outline Creation.

After creating the outlines, the next step was Material Production and Distribution, which involved utilizing digital tools to design and print materials that were accessible and engaging. These materials were distributed to students, ensuring they could easily understand and follow the lessons. In Interactive Lesson Delivery, the outlines were implemented in classroom sessions supplemented with interactive discussions and activities to enhance engagement and understanding. Teachers used interactive methodologies to make the lessons more effective and efficient.

Finally, in Assessment and Feedback, evaluations were conducted to measure students' mastery and gather feedback for continuous improvement. The input was used to refine the process and ensure that the curriculum's key elements were effectively translated into accessible content and engagingly delivered. Their impact was accurately measured for iterative refinement.

b. Project Management

The teacher played a key role in effectively implementing the ILOK approach. A management strategy was implemented, which involved setting clear objectives, creating detailed timelines, and collecting student feedback. The teacher was responsible for preparing and guiding the use of ILOK materials and continuously adapting and improving the learning experience. This collaborative process ensured that innovation was aligned with educational goals and student needs.

c. Timeline

The pre-implementation phase for this innovation involved the teacher innovator conducting a detailed curriculum review to ensure alignment with the Most Essential Learning Competencies, designing ILOK materials, creating visual aids and interactive elements, and preparing all necessary materials. During the one-week implementation phase, teachers introduced the ILOK materials and a study lesson outline for Araling Panlipunan 5 and explained how to use them effectively. Each day, the lesson outlines were implemented in classroom sessions, supplemented by interactive discussions, activities, and real-time feedback to adjust teaching methods. A comprehensive review session was con-

<p style="text-align: center;">Pagbabago sa Edukasyon</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ang pangunahing layunin ng edukasyonay pagtuturo ng Kristiyanismo, pagbasa, pagsulat at pagkuwenta. • Mahigpit ang pagdidisiplina sa mga mag-aaral. Ang hindi makapagsaulo ng aralin ay pinaparusahan. Kaya naman lakot ang mga mag-aaral sa mga nagtuturo sa karila. • Nawala ang pagkakataon namalalang at matutunan ng mga Pilipino ang sariling kultura dahil sa mga kulturang itinuturo ng mga Espanyol. • Ang Unibersidad ng Santo Tomas ang pinakamatandang unibersidad sa Pilipinas. Itinatagito sa Pilipinas noong Abril 28, 1611. Karamihan ng nag-aaral dito noon ay mga anak ng mga opisyal na Espanyol at ng mga mayayamang pamilyang mestizo. <p style="text-align: center;">Pagbabago sa Kulturang Pilipino</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pagbabago sa Paniniwala at Relihiyon. Paniniwala sa Langit, Impiyerno at Purgatorio. 2. Pagbabago sa Pangalan at Apelyido. Mula sa pangalang Liwayway, Makisig, Bayani ay napalitan tulad ng Juan, Corazon, Tomas at iba pa. 3. Pagkakaroon ng mga Paaralan na nagtuturo din ng Kristiyanismo. 4. Pagbabago sa Musika at Sayaw. 5. Pagbabago sa Kaugalian at Tradisyon. Pagrorosaryo, Pista, Pasko, Sama-samang pagdadasal ng mag-anak. 6. Pagbabago ng Pananamit at Kasuotan. 7. Ang kulturang dala ng mga Espanyol ay nakasentro sa relihiyong Kristiyanismo. 8. May mga naiambag na mabuting kultura ang mga Espanyol at mayroon ding nakasama sa mga Pilipino. 	<p style="text-align: center;">ILOK of Grade 5 Students (Instructional Lesson Outline for Kids) A Study Outline for Araling Panlipunan 5 Ikatlong Markahan</p> <p>Name: _____</p> <p>Section: _____</p> <hr style="border: 1px solid red;"/> <p style="text-align: center;">Mga Uri ng Buwis (Tributo)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tributo - unang uri ng buwis na nagkakahalaga ng 8 reales, na katagalan lumaas ng 15 reales. • Tithe o diezos prediales - buwis na binabayaran para sa simbahan. • Bandala - kota ng produktong kailangang ipagbili ng mga mamamayan sa pamahalaan. • Cedula - resibo na may pagkakilanlan na kinukuha at binabayaran ng mga mamamayang 18 gulang pataas. Nakalagay dito ang kanyang pangalan, lahi at liranhan. Kailangan itong dalhin palagi. <p style="text-align: center;">Ugnayan ng Simbahan at Pamahalaang Kolonyal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conquistador- tawag sa mga mananakop na Espanyol. • Prayle - mga paring Espanyol. Sila ang pumalit sa mga babayan sa kanilang tungkulin bilang lagapag-ugnay sa kultura at relihiyon ng mga Pilipino. Hindi lahat ng mga Prayle ay masama. • Agustino Prayle - unang kongregasyon ng mga prayle na dumating sa Pilipinas kasama si Legazpi. • Patronato Real - isang kasunduan na nagbibigay karapatan sa kaharian ng Espanya na ipakilala at palaganapin ang relihiyong Romano Katoliko. Naging tungkulin ng pamahalaan ang pagtatanggol sa simbahan. • Hacienda - mga malalawak na lupain na ibinibigay ng Hari ng Espanya sa mga prayle. • Doctrina Christiana - kauna-unahang aklat na inilimbag sa Pilipinas. Inilimbag ito ng mga paring Dominikano noong 1593. Nakasulat dito ang mga doktrina at katesismong dapat maikuturo sa mga Pilipino.
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Fig. 1: Sample ILOK 1

<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Buhay at paniniwala sa pagpapakalat ng Kristiyanismo</u></p> <p>A. Pagbibinyag ng mga misyonero sa mga katutubosa mga malalayong lugar at kabundukan; B. Pagpapakilala sa mga okayson tulad ng Pasko, pista at Mahal na Araw; C. Pagpapalit sa salitang Bathala sa salitang Diyos (Dios); D. Paninira at pagsasantabi sa mga Babaylan; E. Pagtatayo ng Paaralang Katoliko; F. Pagpapalaganap ng panitikang Espanyol;</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Reaksyon ng mga Pilipinosa Kristiyanismo</u></p> <p>A. Sumampalataya ng lubosat sumunod sa relihiyon; B. Nag-alsa at nakipaglaban; C. Tahimik at pasekretong bumalik sa dating pananampalataya; D. Nagpakalayu-layo para hindi sila maratingng mga pari.</p> <p>Pamahalaang Kolonyal ng mga Espanyol</p> <p>Visitador - opisyal ng pamahalaan ng Espanya na ipinadadala sa kolonya upang siyasatin ang paraan ng pamamahala rito</p> <p>A. Pamahalaang Sentral</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gobernador-Heneral – Kinatawan ng Hari ng Espanya Nagpapatupad ng batas. Pinuno ng militar. 2. Real Audidencia - Pinakamataas na Hukuman. Tagapayo ng Gobernador-Heneral. <p>B. Pamahalaang Lokal</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Alcalde Mayor- Pinuno ng lalawigang mapayapa o Alcaldia. 2. Corregidor- Pinuno ng lalawigang may kaguluhan o Corregimiento. 3. Gobernadorcillo- Pinunong Pueblo o Bayan. May ibigsabihing "Malitna Gobernador". 4. Alcalde - Pinunong isang lungsod o Ayuntamiento. 5. Cabeza de Barangay- Pinuno ng Barangay. 	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Panahanan sa panahon ng Espanyol</u></p> <p>A. Rekonsentrasyon - Pinagsasama-sama at inililipat ng mga Espanyol ang mga Pilipinong nasa malalayong lugar; B. Magkakalapit ang mga tahanan; C. Mas naging malaki ang maraming kabahayan at dumami ang mga bahagi nito; D. Nagkaroon ng mga bahay na gawa sa bato; E. Kadalasang natatagpuan ang simbahan sa gitna ng kumunidad o sa sentro ng poblacion;</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Kababaihan sa Panahon ng Espanyol</u></p> <p>A. Sa bahay lamang nag-aasekaso sa pamilya; B. Tumatangap sa sahod ng kanilang asawa; C. Hindi dapat nakikisalamuha sa mga kalalakihan; D. Dapat may kasamapagdumadalo sa mga kasayahan; E. Hindi kailangan magkaroonng mataas na pinag-aralan; F. Sinasanay maging mabuti at mapagmahal na ina at asawa; G. Sentro sa buhaynila ang Pamilya at Relihiyon;</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Antas ng Lipunan sa Panahon ng Espanyol</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Principalia binubuong mga mayayamang may-ari ng lupain, mga inapo ng datu, mga guro at mga pinunong bayan. Maaari silang bumoto sa lokal na halalan at humawak ng posisyon sa pamahalaan. 2. Inquilino – mga taong nangangasiwa ng mga lupain. 3. Kasama – mga tauhang pinipiling mga Inquilino upang magsaka at magtrabaho sa mga lupain. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peninsulares – tawag sa mga may purong dugong Espanyol. Ang ama at ina nila ay puro mga Espanyol. • Insulares – tawag sa mga anak ng mga Espanyol na nakapag-asawa ng Pilipino o iba pang Asyano. Tinatawag din silang mga Mestizo. • Indio – tawag ng mga Espanyol sa mga Pilipino. Ang indio ay katumbas ng pagiging mangmango walang alam, tamad, at alipin.
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Fig. 2: Sample ILOK 2

ducted at the end of the week, and a summative assessment was concluded to measure mastery of the week's objectives. During the post-implementation phase, the ILOK innovation was presented in LAC sessions as an example of how it can be used in Araling Panlipunan or other learning areas. Feed-

back and evaluations were conducted to gather insights that could be used to explore its effectiveness. The input received could be used to modify the materials, improve the support systems, or revise the implementation plans. Furthermore, the potential of innovation for growth is considered to expose

Fig. 3: Process Flow

more learners to even more learning possibilities in other educational contexts or subject areas. However, it is essential to note that this innovation is adaptive to new ideas and learning methods better to suit the needs of both learners and teachers.

d. Resource Utilization

The ILOK innovation relied heavily on a variety of resources that were essential for its success. These resources included educational content, digital design tools, printers, bond paper, and the expertise of teachers. However, the most critical resource for the ILOK approach was human capital, especially teachers' innovative and creative skills. It was their knowledge that was central to developing and implementing this approach. Efficiently managing these resources was a crucial part of the ILOK approach. This was achieved through strategic planning and scheduling, ensuring materials were prepared and distributed in time for classroom use. Resource allocation emphasized minimizing waste and maximizing the impact of educational materials on student learning. This ensured that the available resources were utilized to their maximum potential. Several strategies were employed to ensure that the resources were used optimally. Teachers used Microsoft 365 from DepEd to provide MS Word and MS Presentation software. Bulk purchase of printing supplies and using recycled materials for printing was another way to minimize costs. Additionally, continuous teacher training was offered to improve the creation and delivery efficiency of ILOK materials. This approach focused on essential resources and iterative refinement based on feedback,

ensuring cost-effectiveness and sustainability.

e. Progress Monitoring

The teacher is primarily responsible for monitoring the progress and outcomes, implementing the ILOK approach, and collecting data on student engagement, understanding, and performance. They play a critical role in evaluating the effectiveness of educational innovation in real-time. The process includes regular assessments, feedback collection, and classroom observation. Teachers employ formative and summative assessments to gauge learning outcomes and adjust teaching methods accordingly.

Tools for progress monitoring include spreadsheets for tracking performance data and Journals for their insights. These tools aid in collecting, analyzing, and reporting data to inform decisions and continuously improve the ILOK approach.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

The teacher plans to use the ILOK approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan 5 throughout the school year. The innovative materials are stored in clear books for easy accessibility. By consistently using this approach, more learners can master the concept. Providing support to learners is important for maintaining its effectiveness. This dynamic innovation can be modified and refined to improve its efficacy. It is important to consider results and feedback from teachers and learners using this approach. Collaboration with educa-

Outputs/ Outcomes (Enumerates the outputs or outcomes produced from this innovation)	Beneficiary/ies (Who benefited from corresponding results or outcomes)
Improved student engagement, enhanced understanding of Araling Panlipunan concepts, and higher proficiency levels.	The beneficiaries are the Grade Five learners who gain a more accessible and engaging learning experience and teachers, who achieve more effective teaching outcomes and enhanced learner performance.

Fig. 4: Outputs and Beneficiaries

tional researchers and experts is highly encouraged to continuously improve teachers' creative teaching methods, techniques, and strategies. This approach promotes an inclusive learning environment that enhances academic performance and achievement.

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